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The Transformative Influence of Motivation on Organizational Behavior

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Abstract

The study examines the organizational and motivational practices of 102 secondary school teachers across two institutions Chittagong Bangladesh. The study, which uses statistical analysis tools like SPSS and a descriptive analytical methodology, finds that employees are most influenced by the opportunity to take part in training programs, get transportation subsidies, and have a voice in corporate decision-making when such opportunities are provided. Positive markers of organizational behavior include respect, steadily rising performance, and successful learning. Teachers with fewer than eight years of experience and those with less than three years of experience had a greater influence on students' motivation, according to the study. However, the effect of motivation does not vary much with either sex or educational level. These results contribute to our understanding of what drives teachers in this context and have consequences for schools and future study.

Keyword: Teacher Motivations, organizational behavior, performance improvement, Descriptive analytical technique, educational institutions

1. Introduction

In addition to subject-specific and pedagogical abilities, teachers are also responsible for planning, administrative work, extracurricular activities, innovative teaching methods, teamwork, and character development. Educational institutions need a catalyst to increase effectiveness and develop internationally competitive educational systems because of the critical role that instructors play and their widespread lack of competency. Positive results and a supportive work environment have been linked to organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), which is recognized in organizational behavior for going above and beyond job responsibilities. Teachers are key players in schools, and total performance depends on their OCB. Like businesses that rely on human resources, schools also rely on OCB to carry out their daily operations. Given this, all educators ought to internalize OCB. Given the importance of OCB, it is necessary to cultivate an OCB environment in schools. Organizational, societal, and individual elements all have an impact on OCB, with the principal serving as a strategic leader. A transformative leadership style is seen to be appropriate for improving OCB behavior in schools, since it can have an influence on teacher OCB. Through personalized attention and inspiration, transformational leaders inspire their team members, motivating them to work harder and building mutual respect inside the company. Student academic attainment, work culture, classroom atmosphere, and teacher efficacy have all improved in schools under transformational leadership. Another important component of OCB is motivation, which affects work satisfaction and, in turn, OCB behavior. High-achieving, devoted, and willing people are the result of intrinsic motivation. Since each instructor is distinct and has a varied set of

incentives, motivation becomes a catalyst for both organizational and individual success. It is essential to do research on OCB and the factors that influence it, particularly in the context of education. Teacher motivation and the principal's transformational leadership style work together to impact OCB, which may have favorable effects on teacher effectiveness and general educational quality. The goal of this study is to better understand how motivation, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), and transformational leadership style interact in a classroom setting. With an emphasis on the crucial responsibilities played by educators and school principals, the study seeks to understand how motivating elements in conjunction with the creative and inspiring elements of transformational leadership impact educators' optional actions beyond official employment duties. Through investigating these processes within the educational setting, the study hopes to provide insightful information that can expedite the improvement of educational quality. It is seen to be essential to comprehend how motivation and leadership styles influence the behaviors of educators, including principals, in order to provide a pleasant learning environment and enhance student performance in general.

2. Literature review

The diverse duties that teachers have, which include subject-matter competence, administrative work, involvement in extracurricular activities, creative teaching, teamwork, and character development. It is acknowledged that instructors generally lack competency, despite the critical role they serve. In order to improve educational institutions' efficacy and promote internationally competitive educational systems, there is a need for a catalyst or driving force (Ainscow, 2020). It presents the idea of organizational citizenship behavior, as it relates to organizational behavior and emphasizes its applicability to the educational setting. Positive results and a supportive work atmosphere are linked to OCB, which is defined by acts that go above and beyond job requirements (Pitaloka & Sofia, 2014). Teachers are seen as key players in the classroom, and participation in OCB is considered necessary for success in the end. The comparison is made between how businesses depend on human resources for day-to-day operations and how schools depend on OCB (Suriansyah et al., 2019). The story acknowledges the importance of OCB and emphasizes the necessity of creating an environment in schools that is supportive of OCB. It highlights the importance of the principal's strategic position as a leader and presents the three impacting factors: organizational, social, and individual. One important aspect impacting teacher OCB is the principal's leadership style; transformational leadership is preferred when it comes to improving OCB behavior in schools (Naully et al., 2022). Motivating, providing individualized attention, and cultivating a mutually beneficial connection are the hallmarks of this technique, which has been shown to have favorable effects on student academic attainment, work culture, homework atmosphere, and teacher efficacy (Darling-Hammond & Cook-Harvey, 2018). Another important component impacting OCB is motivation, which is shown to have an impact on work satisfaction and OCB behavior in turn (Rinaldi & Riyanto, 2021). High performance and voluntary commitment are hallmarks of intrinsic motivation, which is highlighted as a success factor for both individuals and organizations (Millette & Gagné, 2008). The story takes into account the variety of reasons teachers have for teaching and emphasizes motivation as a factor in both individual and organizational success. The relevance of OCB research and its affecting elements in the context of education is emphasized in the passage's conclusion (Cohen & Liu, 2011). The transformational leadership style of the principal and teacher motivation have a synergistic effect on OCB, with good consequences for teacher competency and overall quality of education (Purwanto, 2022).

3. Research Methodology

The study, which is categorized as non-experimental, was carried out with the intention of investigating how motivation and transformational leadership affect organizational citizenship behavior in a public primary school in Chittagong, Bangladesh. The study employed a proportional random sampling technique to pick 196 instructors from 102 schools in Chittagong, Bangladesh, using a quantitative approach and survey methodology. On a 5-point Likert scale, from 1 (never) to 5 (often or always), respondents provided their answers. The Cronbach's alpha for the questionnaire was displayed. The questionnaire had a Likert scale with a range of 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), and it showed a Cronbach's alpha. The third variable under

investigation, motivation, was assessed using a two-factor theory-based questionnaire consisting of 29 questions spread across 10 dimensions. The first group of elements addressed motivation, including development, responsibility, accomplishment, acknowledgment, the work itself, and progress. Company policies were among the hygienic elements considered in the second set. A 5-point Likert scale, with 1 denoting strongly disagree and 5 denoting strongly agree, is used in the motivation questionnaire. Several necessary tests were run once the data were gathered, including the t-test, multicollinearity test, heteroscedasticity test, correlation coefficient test, normality test, and significance and linearity test. After that, the hypothesis will be tested partially or concurrently using the t-test and f-test to ascertain the impact between variables. SPSS was used to examine the data.

4. Results and Discussions

Table 1 shows that the outcomes of the clarifying data for Groundbreaking administration, Inspiration, and Hierarchical Citizenship Conduct. The information was tested using the significance and relapse coefficient linearity test, the multicollinearity test, the heteroskedasticity test, the linearity test, the homogeneity test, the linearity test, and the ordinariness test before a method study was carried out. The result of the Kolmogorov Smirnov ordinariness test for a sym-sig (2-followed) is 0.66, indicating a high probability that the data was within usual reach.

Table 1. Summary of statistics data of the research

Analysis	Organizational Citizenship behavior	Transformational Leadership	Motivation
n	102	102	102
Minimum score	68	91	86
Maximum score	141	142	164
Range	49	52	61
Mode	116	116	151
Mean	112.01	109.26	142.82
Std. Deviation	13.02	11.248	14.245
Variance	146.21	124.25	186.14

The results of the linearity experiment show that the correlation between innovative initiative and hierarchical citizenship conduct is $F\text{-linearity} = 144,095$; the correlation between authoritative citizenship conduct and inspiration is $F\text{-linearity} = 161,166$. It is implied from the data results that there was a direct correlation between the variables. When the multicollinearity test resistance esteem is 0,466 (higher than 0,100) and VIF 2,66 (less than 10,00), it is generally assumed that there are no multicollinearity-related side effects in the data. The results of the Glejser heteroscedasticity test show that the significance and motivation for breakthrough authority are both 0.865, which is more notable than 0.05, and 0.414, which is more noteworthy than 0.05. Generally speaking, it is assumed that there is no heteroscedasticity problem. Lastly, relationship tests are used in the review to determine the link between the elements. The correlation coefficient between the innovative initiative and the hierarchical civic behavior is 0.6966. There is a correlation of 0.644% between inspiration and hierarchical citizenship behavior, and a correlation of 0.690 between inspiration and innovative administration. The all-out coefficient of certainty of 0,586 is displayed in Table 2. One might reasonably argue that variations in innovative leadership and inspiration account for 58,5% of the variation in authoritative civic behavior. The remaining 41,5% is explained by several components that were left out of the model. Given the implications of the different straight relapse examinations presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Coefficient of Determination Value

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate

.665a

0.585

0.566

6.46464

The innovative administration and inspiration have a moderate impact on hierarchical civic behavior. H₀ is rejected and H_a is recognized based on the factual t-esteem = 2,865 (more notable than 1,651) and p-esteem = 0,005 (not precisely $\alpha = 0,05$) of this ground-breaking administration on authoritative citizenship behavior. Consequently, innovative initiative and hierarchical citizenship behavior have a very strong beneficial relationship. The genuine t-esteem = 5,116 (more notable than 1,651) and p-esteem 0,000 (not precisely $\alpha = 0,05$) inspire authoritative civic conduct. As such, H_a is recognized while H₀ is rejected. And it suggests that hierarchical citizenship behavior and inspiration have a crucially favorable relationship. Table 3 displays the path coefficient association between the variables.

Table.3. Path Coefficient and T-Test

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	t _{table}	Sig.	Result
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	16.265	6.642		2.105		0.048	
Motivation	0.425	0.084	0.515	5.116	1.651	0	Significant
Transformational Leadership	0.411	0.108	0.289	2.865	1.651	0.005	Significant

Table 4 illustrates how inspirational leadership and ground-breaking authority simultaneously shape hierarchical civic behavior. From the quantifiable F-esteem = 66,645 (more significant than 4,068) and sig esteem = 0,000 (less than 0,05), it tends to be closed. Thus, innovative initiative and inspiration simultaneously impact authoritative civic behavior. The three factors show that they positively impact one another based on the results of the t-test and f-test.

Table 4. Analysis of Variance

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F _{empiric}	F _{table}	Sig.	Result
Regression	8446.665	2	4164.449	66.645	4,068	.000b	Significant
Residual	5928.159	109	54.486				
Total	14264.86	111					

The findings are based on data collected from 102 teachers in 10 public schools. The analysis of coefficients indicates a direct and positive influence of transformational leadership on OCB. The transformational leadership improves, OCB also sees enhancements. Transformational leaders are seen as role models, and school principals with high social skills and success levels are found to increase OCB in their organizations (Qalati et al., 2022). The importance of the inspirational motivation dimension in transformational leadership, urging school principals to incorporate it into their leadership styles. However, the impact of the intellectual stimulation dimension, which is crucial for encouraging innovation among followers. Despite previous research exploring the link between transformational leadership and OCB, uniquely focuses on the educational context, suggesting that adopting a transformational leadership style is crucial for increasing OCB in schools (Somech & Ohayon, 2020). Motivation is recognized as a key factor driving employees to fulfill their duties with awareness, enthusiasm, and responsibility. The study aligns with previous research findings, emphasizing the importance of maintaining high levels of teacher motivation to foster OCB in schools (Dobre, 2013). The finding aligns with previous research linking transformational leadership with task performance in government business lecturers. Principals, as transformational leaders, play a crucial role in motivating and inspiring teachers through guidance and counseling, ultimately contributing to the success of both teachers and students (Andriani et al., 2018). The relationships between transformational leadership, motivation, and OCB among teachers in the specified context (Majeed et al., 2017).

5. Conclusions

The purpose of this research is to investigate the relationship between hierarchical civic conduct (OCB), instructor motivation, and pioneering authority in Philippine elementary schools located in the Area Pinang region. The study comes to the conclusion that OCB is influenced by both pioneering initiatives and instructor motivation. In order to improve OCB in schools, the review suggests that administrators should use innovative authority methods. At the same time, teachers should continue to maintain high levels of inspiration in order to contribute to this outcome. In addition, the research emphasizes the relevance of collaborative efforts between school administrators and teachers in order to foster a higher level of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in educational institutions. When it comes to the implementation of the review, however, there are certain limitations. For instance, the review relies solely on the survey technique inside the Google Structure program for the collection of information, and there is almost no observational data. The next generation of scientists is strongly encouraged to construct their own example measurements and to think about remembering different elements for research that are similar. Undergraduate students who are focused on educational administration may find this examination useful since it provides insights into the ways in which innovative authority and educator inspiration may influence organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in educational circumstances.

References

- i. Ainscow, M. (2020). Promoting inclusion and equity in education: lessons from international experiences. *Nordic Journal of Studies in Educational Policy*, 6(1), 6-16.
- ii. Pitaloka, E., & Sofia, I. P. (2014). The effect of work environment, job satisfaction, organization commitment on OCB of internal auditors. *International Journal of Business, Economics and Law*, 5(2), 10-18.
- iii. Suriansyah, A., Aslamiah, A., Noorhapizah, N., Winardi, I., & Dalle, J. (2019). The relationship between university autonomy, lecturer empowerment, and organizational citizenship behavior in Indonesian universities. *Journal of Social Studies Education Research*, 10(4), 126-152.
- iv. Rinaldi, E., & Riyanto, S. (2021). The effect of work motivation, work environment, and job satisfaction on organizational citizenship behavior and their impact on employee's performance of RSU Menteng Mitra Afia during the Covid-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* (2146-4468), 10(6), 101-110.
- v. Naully, M., Purba, S., & Gultom, I. (2022). The influence of mindfulness, collective values, transformational leadership, working conditions, psychological empowerment on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) among high school teachers in Medan. *Randwick International of Social Science Journal*, 4(2), 491-406.
- vi. Darling-Hammond, L., & Cook-Harvey, C. M. (2018). *Educating the Whole Child: Improving School Climate to Support Student Success*. Learning Policy Institute.
- vii. Cohen, A., & Liu, Y. (2011). Relationships between in-role performance and individual values, commitment, and organizational citizenship behavior among Israeli teachers. *International journal of psychology*, 46(4), 261-286.
- viii. Millette, V., & Gagné, M. (2008). Designing volunteers' tasks to maximize motivation, satisfaction and performance: The impact of job characteristics on volunteer engagement. *Motivation and emotion*, 42, 11-22.
- ix. Purwanto, A. (2022). Elementary school teachers' performance: how the role of transformational leadership, competency, and self-efficacy? *International Journal of Social and Management Studies (IJOSMAS)*.
- x. Andriani, S., Kesumawati, N., & Kristiawan, M. (2018). The influence of the transformational leadership and work motivation on teachers' performance. *International journal of scientific & technology research*, 7(7), 19-29.

- xi. Dobre, O. I. (2013). Employee motivation and organizational performance. Review of applied socio-economic research, 5(1).
- xii. Qalati, S. A., Zafar, Z., Fan, M., Limón, M. L. S., & Khaskheli, M. B. (2022). Employee performance under transformational leadership and organizational citizenship behavior: A mediated model. Heliyon, 8(11).
- xiii. Somech, A., & Ohayon, B. E. (2020). The trickle-down effect of OCB in schools: The link between leader OCB and team OCB. Journal of Educational Administration, 58(6), 629-643.